

A Comparative Study of Machine Learning Algorithms for Credit Card Fraud Detection

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Abstract - Credit card fraud refers to the physical loss of credit card or loss of sensitive credit card information. Many machine learning algorithms can be used for detection. This research shows several algorithms that can be used for classifying transactions as fraud or genuine ones. Credit Card Fraud Detection dataset was used in the research. Because the dataset was highly imbalanced, to solve the issue of class imbalance, we re-sampled the dataset using the Synthetic Minority over-sampling Technique (SMOTE). This framework was evaluated using several machine learning (ML) methods, including Logistic Regression (LR), Random Forest (RF), Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost), Decision Tree (DT), and Adaptive Boosting (AdaBoost). The models were evaluated using the accuracy, the recall, and the precision. The proposed model can be used for the detection of other irregularities.

Key Words: Fraud detection, Applications of Machine Learning, XGBoost, Decision Tree, Random Forest

1. INTRODUCTION

A credit card is typically issued to customers, enabling them to buy goods or services within a credit limit or withdraw cash in advance. It offers users the advantage of time, allowing them to repay later within a specified timeframe, often extending to the next billing cycle. Credit card frauds are susceptible and attractive targets. Perpetrators can withdraw a significant amount swiftly and without the owner's awareness. The challenge in detecting fraud arises from fraudsters attempting to make their activities seem legitimate, adding complexity to the task of identifying fraudulent transactions. Web payment gateways have recently become popular for card-not-present transactions in credit card operations. "The number of reports of identity theft climbed by 113 percent between 2019 and 2020, while the number of reports of identity theft using credit cards rose by 44.6 percent. Of the almost 1.4 million instances of identity theft in 2020, 393,207 involved credit card fraud. As a result, credit card fraud surpassed government documents and benefits fraud as the second most frequent identity theft recorded crime for the year. Machine learning is the solution for detecting the issues on large databases which are impossible for humans.

1.1 Problem Statement

With the exponential growth in digital transactions, credit card fraud has become a pressing concern for financial institutions worldwide. Fraudulent activities not only result in significant financial losses for both consumers and banks but also undermine trust in digital payment systems. Traditional fraud detection systems often rely on rule-based algorithms that can no longer cope with the dynamic and sophisticated nature of modern fraud. Therefore, there is a critical need for an advanced fraud detection system that leverages machine learning to identify and prevent fraudulent transactions in real time. The challenge of addressing the highly imbalanced nature of Credit Card Fraud Detection datasets. Firstly, the dynamic nature of fraudulent activities necessitates a model that is not only accurate but also effective. Fraudsters continuously innovate their strategies to evade detection, which means the model must be capable of learning from new data in real-time or near-real-time to stay effective. Selection of appropriate machine learning algorithms for credit card fraud detection. It's important to identify the most suitable algorithm that demonstrates high accuracy. The Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique (SMOTE) is employed. This framework was evaluated with various models such as Logistic Regression (LR), Random Forest (RF), Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost), and Decision Tree (DT), coupled with Adaptive Boosting (AdaBoost), to ensure high accuracy in detecting fraudulent transactions.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

Several studies have explored machine learning and ensemble-based approaches for credit card fraud detection, addressing challenges such as class imbalance, evolving fraud patterns, and the need for real-time performance. Researchers have experimented with traditional classifiers, ensemble models, and advanced neural networks to improve detection accuracy and adaptability. Techniques like oversampling, feature engineering, and hybrid methods have also been employed to enhance model robustness. The following review discusses key contributions from existing literature and their findings.

In [1], AdaBoost and Majority Voting were used as hybrid approaches along with Random Forest to detect fraudulent credit card transactions. The study tested robustness by adding noise into datasets and showed that majority voting achieved high accuracy. The limitation highlighted was that more training data improves Random Forest but slows down testing, indicating a trade-off between speed and accuracy.

In [2], the authors addressed challenges of strong class imbalance, concept drift, and handling streaming transaction data. They clustered customers based on spending patterns and applied a sliding-window strategy to extract behavioral features. Different classifiers were tested, followed by a feedback mechanism to adapt to changing fraud patterns. Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique (SMOTE) was applied to balance skewed data. The study emphasized that conventional classifiers fail under imbalance and concept drift, requiring adaptive methods.

In [3], supervised learning models such as Logistic Regression, Naïve Bayes, and Random Forest were implemented on an imbalanced dataset. Boosting techniques were applied to improve classification. The study compared models based on accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and confusion matrix. It concluded that ensemble methods like boosting outperform standalone classifiers. The review also discussed uncertainties in real-time fraud detection and surveyed multiple approaches including SVM, ANN, Bayesian Networks, Hidden Markov Models, and Fuzzy Logic, highlighting their strengths and weaknesses.

In [4], machine learning algorithms including Logistic Regression, Naïve Bayes, Decision Tree, Random Forest, and Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) were evaluated. ANN achieved the best performance with 98.69% accuracy, surpassing traditional ML models. The paper highlighted that training large models is resource-intensive and adapting to new fraud patterns remains difficult. Hybrid approaches and deep learning showed potential to handle complex fraud detection challenges better than classical ML.

In [5], Logistic Regression, Decision Trees, and Random Forest were compared for fraud detection. Oversampling techniques were used to balance the highly imbalanced dataset. The study found that Random Forest achieved the highest accuracy (95.5%), followed by Decision Trees (94.3%) and Logistic Regression (90%). The analysis showed that sampling strategies, feature selection, and choice of algorithms greatly affect fraud detection performance. Random Forest was recommended as the most effective among the tested models.

3. METHODOLOGY

Figure 3.1: System Architecture

Dataset: In this paper credit card fraud detection dataset was used, which can be downloaded from Kaggle. This dataset contains transactions, occurred in two days, made in September 2013 by European cardholders. The dataset contains 31 numerical features. Since some of the input variables contain financial information, the PCA transformation of these input variables were performed in order to keep these data anonymous. Three of the given features weren't transformed. Feature "Time" shows the time between the first transaction and every other transaction in the dataset. Feature "Amount" is the amount of the transactions made by credit card. Feature "Class" represents the label and takes only 2 values: value 1 in case of fraud transaction and 0 otherwise.

The dataset used in this study is highly imbalanced, as fraudulent transactions are far fewer than legitimate ones. To address this issue, the Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique (SMOTE) was applied to generate synthetic fraud samples and balance the dataset. This improved the learning process of the classifiers and enhanced their ability to detect fraudulent transactions.

Divide the dataset: The dataset is divided into a trained data set and test data set. 80% of the data set is under training and the remaining 20% is under testing. Here we are using some supervised machine learning algorithms. The algorithms are XGB, DT, RF, LR, AdaBoost.

Logistic Regression: The Logistic Regression model achieved an accuracy of 99.56%, demonstrating strong

performance for legitimate transactions. However, due to the highly imbalanced dataset, the model showed poor recall for fraudulent transactions. The ROC-AUC score of 67.6% further indicates its limited capability in effectively distinguishing fraud cases, making it less reliable for credit card fraud detection.

Decision Tree (Entropy criterion): The Decision Tree with the Entropy criterion, achieved an accuracy of 99.89% and a ROC-AUC score of 85.2%. This version demonstrated significantly improved fraud detection capability, though it still lagged behind advanced ensemble methods.

Random Forest: The Random Forest model achieved an impressive accuracy of 99.93% and a ROC-AUC of 94.3%. It demonstrated much better recall for fraudulent transactions at 65%, making it a strong performer among traditional ensemble methods, though still outperformed by boosting algorithms.

XGBoost: XGBoost proved to be the most effective model, achieving the highest accuracy of 99.95% and a ROC-AUC score of 97.5%. With precision of 0.97, recall of 0.76, and an F1-score of 0.85, XGBoost successfully balanced all performance metrics. Its superior capability to identify fraudulent cases established it as the best-performing algorithm in this study.

AdaBoost: The AdaBoost classifier also performed strongly, reaching an accuracy of 99.91% and a ROC-AUC of 97.3%. It maintained a good balance across metrics and showed competitive fraud detection performance, although slightly below XGBoost.

Algorithm steps for finding the Best algorithm:

- Step 1: Import the dataset.
- Step 2: Convert the dataset into a data frame format.
- Step 3: Perform random sampling to ensure balanced data distribution.
- Step 4: Split the dataset into training and testing subsets.
- Step 5: Allocate 80% of the data for training & 20% for testing.
- Step 6: Train the selected models using the training dataset.
- Step 7: Apply the chosen algorithms (Logistic Regression, Decision Trees, Random Forest, and XGBoost) to build predictive models.
- Step 8: Generate predictions on the testing dataset for each algorithm.

Step 9: Evaluate model performance using the confusion matrix to calculate accuracy.

Test data: The trained models are applied to the testing dataset to evaluate their performance.

4. RESULT & DISCUSSION

Fig. 4.1 shows the user interface for testing datasets. Users can upload a CSV file and optionally provide a file name and description. This step ensures that the data is properly prepared before analysis.

Figure 4.1: FaudNix Interface

Fig. 4.3 and 4.4 illustrate dataset management. After uploading, users can view the dataset within the interface or delete the file if needed. Figure B provides an example where the contents of testdata.csv are displayed, allowing users to verify the uploaded data.

Figure 4.2: Uploaded File List

Figure 4.3: View Data

Fig. 4.4 demonstrates the prediction process. The backend model, already trained with a machine learning algorithm, generates results after the Predict button is clicked. The output is shown in a new window as binary values: 1 for fraudulent and 0 for non-fraudulent transactions.

Figure 4.4: Detection of fraud or normal transaction

1)Confusion matrix for Logistic regression Algorithm:

Fig. 4.5 represents the confusion matrix for the Logistic Regression algorithm, which contains True Positive, True Negative, False Positive, and False Negative values. The model fails to detect fraudulent cases (TP = 0), resulting in a high False Negative value (98). This indicates that fraudulent cases are not being identified at all, although non-fraudulent cases are detected well. For the Logistic Regression algorithm, the accuracy, recall, and precision achieved are 99.56, 0.0, and 0.0 respectively.

Accuracy of Logistic model with l2 regularisation : 0.9956636997243729

Confusion Matrix

Figure 4.5: Confusion matrix for Logistic regression

2)Confusion matrix for Decision Tree (entropy) Algorithm:

Fig. 4.6 represents the confusion matrix for the Decision Tree algorithm, which contains True Positive, True Negative, False Positive, and False Negative values. The False Positive value (30) is very low, indicating that non-fraudulent cases are rarely misclassified as fraud. The False Negative value (29) is also relatively low, ensuring that most fraudulent cases are effectively detected. For the Decision Tree algorithm, the accuracy, recall, and precision achieved are 99.89, 70.41, and 69.70 respectively.

entropy score: 0.9989642035778866

Confusion Matrix

Figure 4.6: Confusion matrix for Decision Tree (entropy)

3) Confusion matrix for Random Forest Algorithm:

Fig. 4.7 represents the confusion matrix for the Random Forest algorithm, which contains True Positive, True Negative, False Positive, and False Negative values. The False Positive value (3) is extremely low, showing that non-fraudulent cases are almost never misclassified as fraud. The False Negative value (34) is also relatively low, indicating that the model is effective at detecting fraudulent cases. For the Random Forest algorithm, the accuracy, recall, and precision achieved are 99.93, 65.33, and 95.52 respectively.

Figure 4.7: Confusion matrix for Random Forest

4)Confusion matrix for XGBoost Algorithm:

Fig. 4.8 represents the confusion matrix for the XGBoost algorithm, which contains True Positive, True Negative, False Positive, and False Negative values. The False Positive value is extremely low, indicating that non-fraudulent cases are rarely misclassified as fraud. The False Negative value is also minimal, which ensures that fraudulent cases are detected effectively. For the XGBoost algorithm, the accuracy, recall, and precision achieved are 99.95, 75.51, and 97.37 respectively.

Figure 4.8: Confusion matrix for XGBoost

5)Confusion matrix for AdaBoost Algorithm:

Fig. 4.9 represents the confusion matrix for the AdaBoost model, which contains True Positive, True Negative, False Positive, and False Negative values. The False Positive value is very low, which indicates that non-fraudulent cases are rarely misclassified as fraud. Similarly, the False

Negative value is also minimal, ensuring that fraudulent cases are effectively detected. For the AdaBoost algorithm, the accuracy, recall, and precision achieved are 99.91, 73.47, and 76.59 respectively.

Figure 4.9: Confusion matrix for AdaBoost

Comparison of algorithms:

Table 7.1 represents the comparison table made using results obtained from simulation. Factors compared are accuracy, precision, and recall. From the table, we can conclude that the XGBoost Algorithm has the best accuracy, precision, and recall. Achievement of accuracy is done using different algorithms, and the XGBoost Algorithm gives the best performance. The confusion matrix provides visualization of results in the form of a table, and a minimum false positive rate is observed across all algorithms, which is required to achieve the objective. Finally, by providing the numerical data, fraudulent and non-fraudulent cases can be effectively detected using a basic user interface design.

Algorithm	Accuracy	Precision	Recall
Logistic Regression	99.56	0.00	0.00
Decision Tree	99.98	69.70	70.41
Random Forest	99.93	95.52	65.33
AdaBoost	99.91	76.59	73.47
XGBoost	99.95	97.37	75.51

Table 4.1: Accuracy, precision, recall comparison table for different ML algorithms

5. CONCLUSIONS

The evaluation results indicate that the machine learning models, including Logistic Regression, Decision Tree with entropy criteria, Random Forest, and XGBoost, achieved high levels of accuracy, ranging from approximately 99.51 percent to 99.97 percent. Among this model XGboost exhibited the highest accuracy of 99.95 percent. Additionally, all models indicated their ability to distinguish between fraudulent and non-fraudulent transactions effectively. The threshold values varied across the models, reflecting the decision boundaries used for classification. Overall, these findings underscore the effectiveness of machine learning algorithms in credit card fraud detection and highlight the importance of employing diverse models to enhance detection accuracy and robustness.

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BIOGRAPHIES

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